

Supplement of

Assessing the global contribution of marine aerosols, terrestrial bioaerosols, and desert dust to ice-nucleating particle concentrations

Marios Chatziparaschos et al.

Correspondence to: Maria Kanakidou (mariak@uoc.gr)

The copyright of individual parts of the supplement might differ from the article licence.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: Location of the data used for comparison in Figures 10, S6 and S7. For further information see *Table SI*

Figure S2: Simulated concentrations of MPOA compared with Mace Head (green) and Amsterdam Island (violet) measurements.

Figure S3: Seasonal variation of simulated number concentrations of PBAP compared to long-term (>4 weeks) FBAP observations compiled by Petersson Sjögren et al. (2023). Continuous lines are observations and dashed lines simulated number concentrations.

Figure S4: Seasonal percentage contribution of a) mineral dust, (b) fungal spores and bacteria and (c) marine organic aerosols calculated by TM4-ECPL where the total $[INP]_{ambient}$ concentration is larger than $0.01m^{-3}$. The black contour lines represent seasonal mean isotherms in $^{\circ}C$.

Figure S5: Seasonal mean concentration of a) mineral dust, b) fungal spores and bacteria and c) marine organic aerosols calculated by TM4-ECPL where the total $[\text{INP}]_{\text{ambient}}$ concentration is larger than 0.01m^{-3} . The black contour lines represent seasonal mean isotherms in $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure S6: Order of magnitude / Logarithm of the deviation of simulated concentrations of INP types from total INP observations, as a function of binned temperatures in °C. INP_{Dust} in yellow, INP_{PBAP} in green, INP_{MPOA} in blue.

Figure S7: Comparison of INP concentrations calculated at the temperature of the measurements against total INP observations accounting for mineral dust (yellow), MPOA (blue), PBAP (green) separated in high, middle and low latitudes.

Table S1: Data sets used for this study. Campaign/data

Campaign/data set	Location	References
Arctic station Barrow/Utqiavik	Arctic	(Wex et al., 2019)
Alert (Canadian Arctic Station)	Arctic	
Arctic station Ny-Ålesund	Arctic	
Station_Nord (Villum Research Station)	Arctic	

<i>PS95 Atlantic Cruise 2015</i>	Atlantic	(Welti et al., 2020)
<i>KAD_Israel</i>	Tel Aviv	(Ardon-Dryer and Levin, 2014)
<i>KAD_South_Pole</i>	South Pole	(Ardon-Dryer et al., 2011)
<i>Conen_Chaumont</i>	Jungfrauoch and Chaumont	(Conen et al., 2015)
<i>CYPRUS BACCHUS/CHARMEX 2015</i>	Forestry Department site, Agia Marina	(Ansmann et al., 2019)
<i>BACCHUS_FRIDGE AMAZONAS</i>	Amazonian Tall Tower Observatory	(Schrod et al., 2020)
<i>CalWater</i>	Coastal California, Airborne	(Fan et al., 2014)
<i>Conen_JFJ</i>	Jungfrauoch	(Conen et al., 2015)
<i>CLACE2014</i>	Jungfrauoch	(Lacher et al., 2021, 2018, 2017) (Boose et al., 2016)
<i>CLACE2013</i>	Jungfrauoch	
<i>CLACE2012</i>	Jungfrauoch	
<i>CalNex</i>	California	(Wang et al., 2012)
<i>CALIMA 2014</i>	Izana observatory, Tenerife	(Boose et al., 2016)
<i>CALIMA 2013</i>	Izana observatory, Tenerife	(Boose et al., 2016)
<i>ISAC-CNR MaceHead BACCHUS Campaign</i>	Mace Head Observatory, Carna, Galway, Ireland	(Rinaldi et al., 2016)
<i>ISAC-CNR SanPietro_Capofiume BACCHUS Campaign</i>	San Pietro Capofiume (BO, Italy)	(Belosi et al., 2017)
<i>ISAC_CNR_MtCimone BACCHUS Campaign</i>	mountain observatory Mt. Cimone	(Rinaldi et al., 2017)
<i>ISAC-CNR Antarctica BACCHUS Campaign</i>	Mario Zucchelli Station, Terranova Bay, Antarctica	(Belosi et al., 2014)
<i>BACCHUS_FRIDGE_SVALBARD Campaign</i>	Zeppelin Observatory, Svalbard/Spitzbergen	(Schrod et al., 2020)
<i>BACCHUS_FRIDGE_MARTINIQUE</i>	Volcanic and Seismologic Observatory, Fonds- Saint-Denis, Martinique, Caribbean	(Schrod et al., 2020)
<i>CSU_CFDC_archive_BEACHON</i>	Manitou Experimental ForestObservatory (MEFO)	(Tobo et al., 2013)

<i>ETH_JFJ_2014</i>	Jungfrauoch High Altitude Research Station	(Lacher et al., 2017)
<i>ETH_JFJ_2016</i>	Jungfrauoch High Altitude Research Station	(Lacher et al., 2017, 2018)
<i>ETH_JFJ_2015</i>	Jungfrauoch High Altitude Research Station	(Lacher et al., 2017)
<i>TROPOS_Cyprus2016</i>	Agia Marina, Xyliatou, Cyprus	(Ansmann et al., 2019; Schrod et al., 2017)
<i>TROPOS_CV_IN</i>	Cape Verde	(Welti et al., 2018)
<i>Yin_China</i>	China	(Yin et al., 2012)
<i>NETCARE_2013</i>	Coastal (West coast of Canada)	(Mason et al., 2015)
<i>Bigg_1969-1989</i>	Australia, Southern Ocean, Argentina, Africa, India, Japan/Korea, Antarctica, Hawaii, Tasmania,	https://www.bacchus- env.eu/in/ (Bigg, 1973, 1990)
<i>NETCARE</i>	Canadian Arctic	(Irish et al., 2019)
<i>ACAPEX</i>	Bodega Bay (California)	(DeMott and Hill, 2016)
<i>CAPRICORN</i>	South of Australia	(McCluskey et al., 2018)
<i>ACE-SPACE</i>	Atlantic	(Welti et al., 2020)

Eq1. Modified normalised mean bias (MNMB)

$$\text{MNMB} = \frac{2}{N} \sum_i \frac{f_i - o_i}{f_i + o_i}$$

References:

- Ansmann, A., Mamouri, R. E., Bühl, J., Seifert, P., Engelmann, R., Hofer, J., Nisantzi, A., Atkinson, J. D., Kanji, Z. A., Sierau, B., Vrekoussis, M., and Sciare, J.: Ice-nucleating particle versus ice crystal number concentration in altocumulus and cirrus layers embedded in Saharan dust: a closure study, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19, 15087–15115, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-15087-2019>, 2019.
- Ardon-Dryer, K. and Levin, Z.: Ground-based measurements of immersion freezing in the eastern Mediterranean, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 14, 5217–5231, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-5217-2014>, 2014.

- Ardon-Dryer, K., Levin, Z., and Lawson, R. P.: Characteristics of immersion freezing nuclei at the South Pole station in Antarctica, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 11, 4015–4024, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-11-4015-2011>, 2011.
- Belosi, F., Santachiara, G., and Prodi, F.: Ice-forming nuclei in Antarctica: New and past measurements, *Atmos. Res.*, 145–146, 105–111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2014.03.030>, 2014.
- Belosi, F., Rinaldi, M., Decesari, S., Tarozzi, L., Nicosia, A., and Santachiara, G.: Ground level ice nuclei particle measurements including Saharan dust events at a Po Valley rural site (San Pietro Capofiume, Italy), *Atmos. Res.*, 186, 116–126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2016.11.012>, 2017.
- Bigg, E. K.: Ice Nucleus Concentrations in Remote Areas, *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 30, 1153–1157, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1973\)030<1153:INCIRA>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1973)030<1153:INCIRA>2.0.CO;2), 1973.
- Bigg, E. K.: Long-term trends in ice nucleus concentrations, *Atmos. Res.*, 25, 409–415, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-8095\(90\)90025-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-8095(90)90025-8), 1990.
- Boose, Y., Sierau, B., Isabel García, M., Rodríguez, S., Alastuey, A., Linke, C., Schnaiter, M., Kupiszewski, P., Kanji, Z. A., and Lohmann, U.: Ice nucleating particles in the Saharan Air Layer, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 16, 9067–9087, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-16-9067-2016>, 2016.
- Conen, F., Rodríguez, S., Hüglin, C., Henne, S., Herrmann, E., Bukowiecki, N., and Alewell, C.: Atmospheric ice nuclei at the high-altitude observatory Jungfraujoch, Switzerland, *Tellus, Ser. B Chem. Phys. Meteorol.*, 67, <https://doi.org/10.3402/tellusb.v67.25014>, 2015.
- DeMott, P. J. and Hill, T. C.: ACAPEX – Ship-Based Ice Nuclei Collections Field Campaign Report, <https://doi.org/10.2172/1253893>, 2016.
- Fan, J., Leung, L. R., Demott, P. J., Comstock, J. M., Singh, B., Rosenfeld, D., Tomlinson, J. M., White, A., Prather, K. A., Minnis, P., Ayers, J. K., and Min, Q.: Aerosol impacts on California winter clouds and precipitation during calwater 2011: Local pollution versus long-range transported dust, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 14, 81–101, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-81-2014>, 2014.
- Irish, V. E., Hanna, S. J., Willis, M. D., China, S., Thomas, J. L., Wentzell, J. J. B., Cirisan, A., Si, M., Leaitch, W. R., Murphy, J. G., Abbatt, J. P. D., Laskin, A., Girard, E., and Bertram, A. K.: Ice nucleating particles in the marine boundary layer in the Canadian Arctic during summer 2014, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19, 1027–1039, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-1027-2019>, 2019.
- Lacher, L., Lohmann, U., Boose, Y., Zipori, A., Herrmann, E., Bukowiecki, N., Steinbacher, M., and Kanji, Z. A.: The Horizontal Ice Nucleation Chamber HINC: INP measurements at Conditions Relevant for Mixed-Phase Clouds at the High Altitude Research Station Jungfraujoch, *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.*, 1–49, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-2017-474>, 2017.
- Lacher, L., DeMott, P. J., Levin, E. J. T., Suski, K. J., Boose, Y., Zipori, A., Herrmann, E., Bukowiecki, N., Steinbacher, M., Gute, E., Abbatt, J. P. D., Lohmann, U., and Kanji, Z. A.: Background Free-Tropospheric Ice Nucleating Particle Concentrations at Mixed-Phase Cloud Conditions, *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, 123, 10,506–10,525, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JD028338>, 2018.
- Lacher, L., Clemen, H. C., Shen, X., Mertes, S., Gysel-Ber, M., Moallemi, A., Steinbacher, M., Henne, S., Saathoff, H., Mohler, O., Hohler, K., Schiebel, T., Weber, D., Schrod, J., Schneider, J., and Kanji, Z. A.: Sources and nature of ice-nucleating particles in the free troposphere at Jungfraujoch in winter 2017, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 16925–16953, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-16925-2021>, 2021.
- Mason, R. H., Si, M., Li, J., Chou, C., Dickie, R., Toom-Sauntry, D., Pöhlker, C., Yakobi-Hancock, J. D., Ladino, L. A., Jones, K., Leaitch, W. R., Schiller, C. L., Abbatt, J. P. D., Huffman, J. A., and Bertram, A. K.: Ice nucleating particles at a coastal marine boundary layer site: Correlations with

- aerosol type and meteorological conditions, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 15, 12547–12566, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-12547-2015>, 2015.
- McCluskey, C. S., Hill, T. C. J., Humphries, R. S., Rauker, A. M., Moreau, S., Stratton, P. G., Chambers, S. D., Williams, A. G., McRobert, I., Ward, J., Keywood, M. D., Harnwell, J., Ponsonby, W., Loh, Z. M., Krummel, P. B., Protat, A., Kreidenweis, S. M., and DeMott, P. J.: Observations of Ice Nucleating Particles Over Southern Ocean Waters, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 45, 11,989–11,997, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL079981>, 2018.
- Petersson Sjögren, M., Alsved, M., Šantl-Temkiv, T., Bjerring Kristensen, T., and Löndahl, J.: Measurement report: Atmospheric fluorescent bioaerosol concentrations measured during 18 months in a coniferous forest in the south of Sweden, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 23, 4977–4992, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-23-4977-2023>, 2023.
- Rinaldi, M., Belosi, F., Nicosia, A., Santachiara, G., Decesari, S., and Cristina, M.: Ice Nucleating Particles at Mace Head during the 2015 BACCHUS campaign through off-line measurements, 18, 15063, 2016.
- Rinaldi, M., Santachiara, G., Nicosia, A., Piazza, M., Decesari, S., Gilardoni, S., Paglione, M., Cristofanelli, P., Marinoni, A., Bonasoni, P., and Belosi, F.: Atmospheric Ice Nucleating Particle measurements at the high mountain observatory Mt. Cimone (2165 m a.s.l., Italy), *Atmos. Environ.*, 171, 173–180, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2017.10.027>, 2017.
- Schrod, J., Weber, D., Drücke, J., Keleshis, C., Pikridas, M., Ebert, M., Cvetković, B., Nickovic, S., Marinou, E., Baars, H., Ansmann, A., Vrekoussis, M., Mihalopoulos, N., Sciare, J., Curtius, J., and Bingemer, H. G.: Ice nucleating particles over the Eastern Mediterranean measured by unmanned aircraft systems, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 17, 4817–4835, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-4817-2017>, 2017.
- Schrod, J., Thomson, E. S., Weber, D., Kossmann, J., Pöhlker, C., Saturno, J., Ditas, F., Artaxo, P., Clouard, V., Saurel, J. M., Ebert, M., Curtius, J., and Bingemer, H. G.: Long-term deposition and condensation ice-nucleating particle measurements from four stations across the globe, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 20, 15983–16006, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-15983-2020>, 2020.
- Tobo, Y., Prenni, A. J., Demott, P. J., Huffman, J. A., McCluskey, C. S., Tian, G., Pöhlker, C., Pöschl, U., and Kreidenweis, S. M.: Biological aerosol particles as a key determinant of ice nuclei populations in a forest ecosystem, *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, 118, 10,100–10,110, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50801>, 2013.
- Wang, B., Laskin, A., Roedel, T., Gilles, M. K., Moffet, R. C., Tivanski, A. V., and Knopf, D. A.: Heterogeneous ice nucleation and water uptake by field-collected atmospheric particles below 273 K, *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, 117, 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012JD017446>, 2012.
- Welti, A., Müller, K., Fleming, Z. L., and Stratmann, F.: Concentration and variability of ice nuclei in the subtropical maritime boundary layer, 5307–5320, 2018.
- Welti, A., Bigg, E. K., Demott, P. J., Gong, X., Hartmann, M., Harvey, M., Henning, S., Herenz, P., Hill, T. C. J., Hornblow, B., Leck, C., Löffler, M., McCluskey, C. S., Rauker, A. M., Schmale, J., Tatzelt, C., and Pinxteren, M. Van: Ship-based measurements of ice nuclei concentrations over the Arctic, Atlantic, Pacific and Southern oceans, 15191–15206, 2020.
- Wex, H., Huang, L., Zhang, W., Hung, H., Traversi, R., Becagli, S., Sheesley, R. J., Moffett, C. E., Barrett, T. E., Bossi, R., Skov, H., Hünerbein, A., Lubitz, J., Löffler, M., Linke, O., Hartmann, M., Herenz, P., and Stratmann, F.: Annual variability of ice-nucleating particle concentrations at different

Arctic locations, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19, 5293–5311, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-5293-2019>, 2019.

Yin, J., Wang, D., and Guoqing, Z.: An Evaluation of Ice Nuclei Characteristics from the Long-term Measurement Data over North China An Evaluation of Ice Nuclei Characteristics from the Long-term Measurement Data over North China, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13143-012-0020-8>, 2012.